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Energy Efficiency and Output of Agro-based Industries in India

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Abstract

The study attempt to evaluate the status of capital and fuel consumption intensity in agro-based industries in India. Annual Survey of Industries (ASI) data from 1996-97 to 2019-20 have been analysed. Agro-based industries have been selected through the National Industrial Classification (NIC) 2008. The food processing (10), Beverages Industry (11), Tobacco Industry (12) and textile manufacturing (13) were included in the study. The study attempted to draw the trend of capital intensity (Per factory Capital), fuel intensity (Fuel consumed per factory) and its relation with output. The analysis shows a significant positive relation between capital increase and fuel consumption and fuel consumption and per factory production.

Keywords: Agro-based Industries, Energy Intensity, Energy Efficiency, Panel Data Regression

Introduction

Agro-based industries play a crucial role in the industrialisation of countries depending on the agriculture sector. The agro-based industries are vital in providing employment and income in rural areas. In rural areas, the production process seems low technology-based or more labour-oriented, but the manufacturing process becomes more capital-oriented in the registered sector. With technological change, energy intake has also been changing, raising environmental issues. In that way, the state where the minimum use of energy to get the maximum possible output is called energy efficiency. Energy efficiency in the industry contributes to decoupling economic growth and environmental impact while reducing industrial energy intensity and improving competitiveness (UNIDO, 2023).

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UNIDO (2014) published the energy efficiency and productivity in African countries and proposed some green investments and industries in the region. Restriction and intensive are required for sustainable production and sustainability of the environment.

Review of Literature

From the economic perspective, energy efficiency focuses on the sustainability of the environment and production maximisation (Batouta, Aouhassi, & Mansouri, 2023). The demand pattern has changed the production scenario, and significant demand needs large production; therefore, production has become more energy-intensive (Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft, 2000). Also, the value of energy has significantly increased during the last two decades. In the near future, demographic changes will lead to an increase in energy demand. Improvement of energy efficiency has become very crucial in the changed industrial atmosphere. The food processing sector widely uses different dehydration and heat techniques to convert raw materials into value-added commodities. The prices of various fuels have increased, and strict norms for Green House Gas (GHG) emission has compelled manufacturer to adopt energy-efficient technology. In that context, energy efficiency through controlling or minimising energy waste is the best practice to conserve and sustain the factory and environment (Wang, 2014).

Soni et al. (2017) examined the energy intensity in the Indian manufacturing sector. The study covered major energy-intensive manufacturing sectors such as Aluminum, Iron and Steel, Textiles and Fertilizer industries. The study seeks to find the variable that impacts energy intake in manufacturing, like labour intensity, plant, and machinery, repairing, use of software or automation, outsourcing, etc. The analysis results show that labour intensity significantly reduces the energy intensity in all industries except fertiliser.

Batouta et al. (2023) reviewed the existing literature that estimates energy efficiency in manufacturing industries. Broadly, it focuses on the multidisciplinary dimension that helps to make the production process more energy efficient. It suggests the strategic plan to use the energy most efficiently with technology selection, managerial decision, and supervising energy use.

Dasgupta et al. (2017) studied the pattern of energy use in the manufacturing industries of India. They analysed the use of energy in favour of the conservation of the environment with the help of productivity growth and energy efficiency in selected manufacturing industries. The technology progress has features of more energy-saving production technic. The study

concluded that in all energy-intensive industries, material and fuel cost holds a significant portion that can negatively impact the cost of production directly in the competitive environment.

India Energy Outlook (2021) mentioned that the Indian manufacturing sector is becoming more and more energy efficient as energy consumption increases GDP by 3% because of the change in the energy sources from traditional to non-traditional.

The literature review shows the energy efficiency measurement and its importance in the present era. A comprehensive study has been conducted to analyse the energy efficiency in the manufacturing sector with the help of production growth, carbon emission patterns, and technological progress. Also, the potential suggestion to improve energy efficiency from the economic and environmental perspective. The energy consumption in agro-based industries seems much required in the Indian manufacturing sector. There may be no intensive research has been taken to evaluate the energy intensity and efficiency at a particular level. The present study evaluates the status of capital and energy intensity in agro-based industries with their current financial values.

Data and Method

The study used secondary data from the Annual Survey of Industries (ASI). The study focused on the agro-based industries at 3-digit classification in National Industrial Classification (NIC) 2008. The main objective of the study is to find out the relationship between fuel and factor intensity. The panel data regression has been performed to identify the direction of capital intensity with energy intensity in a factory.

$$\mathbf{CF=K/NF} \quad \text{-----(1)}$$

Where,

CF = Capital per Factory

K = Capital

NF = Number of Factories

$$\mathbf{ECF = FV/NF} \quad \text{-----(2)}$$

Where,

EIF = Energy Consumed per Factory

FV = Fuel Value

NF = Number of Factories

$$\mathbf{NVAF = NVA/NF} \quad \text{-----(3)}$$

Where,

NVAF= Net Value Added per Factory

NVA = Net Value Added

NF = Number of Factories

Panel data regression was performed to determine the impact of capital intensity on fuel consumption and the impact of fuel consumption on output.

In the equation ε_{it} shows the error term in panel regression.

$$EIF_{it} = \beta_1 CF_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad \text{-----(4)}$$

$$NVAF_{it} = \beta_1 ECF_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad \text{-----(5)}$$

Trends of Capital per Factory and Fuel Consumed per Factory

Table 1 shows the trends of the capital and fuel consumed by factories from 1996-2019. The capital per factory and fuel consumption both increased over the period of time. Among all the agro-based sectors, the highest capital concentration has been seen in the beverages manufacturing industries, where per factory fixed capital was Rs. 42.07 lakh in 1996, which was increased to Rs. 149.68 lakh in 2019. From 2012, the textiles sector became the highest fixed capital per factory. In 2019, Rs. 171.98 fixed capital per factory was noted in the textiles sector. The food processing and tobacco sectors are relatively less capital oriented based on the average capital held by an individual unit. The average fixed capital, energy and output are different when comparing or calculating the factor intensity in an industry with a capital-labour ratio. In that context, the food processing industry seems less capital-intensive because the number of factories hold large share compared to other sectors.

Table 1 Trends of Capital per Factory and Fuel Consumed per Factory

Industry	Food Processing		Beverages		Tobacco		Textiles	
	FC/ Fact	Fuel/ Fact	FC/ Fact	Fuel/ Fact	FC/ Fact	Fuel/ Fact	FC/ Fact	Fuel/ Fact
1996	11.78	73.50	42.07	422.38	0.60	10.31	34.20	166.82
1997	13.21	93.42	47.57	487.62	1.14	12.13	39.07	204.03
1998	15.12	101.00	33.85	321.53	3.71	34.26	50.95	309.20
1999	17.54	118.12	37.21	420.29	3.90	51.22	64.24	360.87
2000	18.10	115.08	50.86	510.65	5.17	56.77	72.47	362.71
2001	19.30	125.28	51.53	552.77	4.53	59.34	69.83	349.04
2002	20.76	138.88	56.76	590.44	5.63	66.16	77.22	351.43
2003	21.99	132.93	62.27	663.65	5.04	58.61	79.38	359.14
2004	23.45	139.86	59.66	625.29	4.78	52.76	85.10	384.53
2005	27.00	153.35	66.35	635.64	5.71	53.16	92.55	452.52
2006	31.05	197.68	84.75	761.46	6.05	68.31	106.42	568.05
2007	33.13	231.70	88.16	793.22	6.36	73.30	117.68	657.36
2008	37.10	118.31	101.12	956.86	6.42	76.56	112.27	644.47
2009	42.33	160.87	110.58	1171.67	11.98	102.38	122.13	730.38

2010	40.70	145.23	94.34	1068.65	7.58	74.66	106.32	584.21
2011	47.71	173.30	130.82	1122.67	9.33	105.92	117.13	627.37
2012	51.35	180.11	111.22	1196.11	10.28	159.44	138.47	643.23
2013	57.11	188.86	125.68	1272.11	11.40	168.50	153.48	1069.81
2014	60.72	219.43	172.20	1537.22	11.85	191.41	158.50	691.30
2015	59.10	240.97	128.27	1272.64	8.98	152.00	174.22	796.09
2016	62.31	255.80	106.27	1412.11	11.01	194.43	168.95	879.16
2017	69.44	270.81	137.84	1454.16	10.97	169.58	176.48	928.24
2018	74.93	569.92	151.48	1685.76	15.10	175.73	188.34	949.21
2019	76.91	576.41	149.68	1756.72	12.58	180.45	171.98	927.14

Source: Annual Survey of Industries (1996-97 to 2019-20)

*Data compiled for the years system followed by MOSPI, like 1996, is data for 1996-97

The fuel consumption shows the value of the average fuel consumed by the individual factory. The average fuel consumption has increased in all sectors. The average beverage factory consume fuel valued at Rs. 1756.72 lakh, while the textiles, food processing and tobacco industries average fuel consumption per factory was RS. 927.14 lakh, 576.41 lakh and 180.45 lakh, respectively. It is important to note that textiles are considered the most fuel-consuming and energy-inefficient industries. Because the energy consumption is higher and the share of the industry is also very high in the country. Beverage industries hold a negligible share in the manufacturing industries of India.

Results and Discussion

The first regression concerns the impact of capital increase in agro-based industries on fuel consumption. The cross-section effect for both analyses show significant prevailing in data which directs the analysis for panel regression, and The Hausman Test value suggests that Random Effect Model is appropriate for both regressions.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FC_FACT	0.111845	0.005752	19.44446	0.0000
C	11.42037	16.33805	0.699004	0.4863
Effects Specification				
			S.D.	Rho
Cross-section random			32.11558	0.8297
Idiosyncratic random			14.55240	0.1703
Weighted Statistics				
R-squared	0.802522	Mean dependent var	5.746946	
Adjusted R-squared	0.800421	S.D. dependent var	32.40709	
S.E. of regression	14.47763	Sum squared resid	19702.57	
F-statistic	382.0020	Durbin-Watson stat	0.563250	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

The regression results focused on the average fuel a factory unit consumes depending on fixed capital per factory (FC_FACT). The results show that fuel intake increases as capital increases in manufacturing. Fixed capital increased by Rs. 1 lakh, leading to an increase in fuel consumption of Rs. 0.11 lakh. The R-square and Adjusted R-squared values show the intensity of the relationship between both variables with 0.802 and 0.800, respectively. The probability of F-statistics shows the suitability of the model.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FUEL_FACT	3.144248	0.334391	9.402922	0.0000
C	62.35882	92.24254	0.676031	0.5007
Effects Specification				
			S.D.	Rho
Cross-section random			178.3923	0.7385
Idiosyncratic random			106.1474	0.2615
Weighted Statistics				
R-squared	0.483845	Mean dependent var		31.17459
Adjusted R-squared	0.478354	S.D. dependent var		147.2168
S.E. of regression	106.3275	Sum squared resid		1062720.
F-statistic	88.11581	Durbin-Watson stat		0.392181
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

The second regression concerns the impact of fuel consumption production in agro-based industries. The production has been considered in NVA form. The results show that increasing fuel intake by Rs. 1 Lakh leads to an NVA increase of Rs. 3.14 lakh, which is significant. The R-square and Adjusted R-squared values show the intensity of the relationship between both variables with 0.483 and 0.478, respectively. The probability of F-statistics shows the suitability of the model.

Conclusion

Capital intensity significantly impacts the fuel consumption of the factory. Both variables are positively correlated, and the intensity of the relationship is also high. It suggests that the more capital-oriented production process leads to more energy consumption. Energy efficiency seems significant and positive in agro-based industries. More energy intake shows better Net Value Addition of the final good. It suggests that over a period, energy efficiency has increased. Technological progress brings energy intensity, but more energy-efficient technology brings more output with less energy consumption. The primary reason for the statement is though the prices of fuels drastically increased during the last decades, comparative NVA seems higher in the sector.

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